

Assessing Representativeness and Bias in Mobile Phone Locational Data

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Locational data derived from mobile phone devices offer significant opportunities for spatiotemporal analysis of human movement patterns. However, such data are rarely complete or socially neutral and always pose challenges related to completeness and representativeness. Completeness issues can arise from device inactivity, data affordability and network limitations. As a result, not all users' locations are continuously tracked. These gaps affect the ability of mobile phone locational data (MPD) to represent human movement patterns accurately.

This study evaluates the impacts of completeness and representativeness of MPD on their usability. We conceptualize completeness as the fraction of hourly intervals during which at least one location point is recorded by a mobile phone. Completeness is calculated across three temporal periods: whole-day, active-hour, and night-hour periods. We define active hours as 7 am to 10 pm based on exploratory analysis of 1,000 random users in Christchurch with at least seven consecutive days of data in 2022. During these hours, location data collected by mobile phones were consistently more frequent than during other times of day. We assess the numbers of users reaching completeness thresholds ranging from 0.1 to 0.9 over a range of consecutive days varying from two to seven days). We also examine how streaks of consecutive days with different completeness thresholds fluctuate throughout the year and relate to significant events, including holidays, COVID-19 restrictions and changes in the data collection process.

We further investigate data usability and representativeness by detecting home location under different completeness thresholds and validating outputs with Census population data for New Zealand. Based on these findings, we identify appropriate completeness levels and consecutive-day indices for different analysis and propose reliability thresholds for MPD selection.

This work contributes scalable methods for evaluating MPD quality, investigating hidden biases, and fostering more transparent, context-aware use of MPD across multiple contexts.